

THE IMPORTANCE OF PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE AND CREATIVITY IN
EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15315480>

Abstract. This study provides information about the main essence of competence and creativity in pedagogical education. It is also stated that teachers are required to have creativity, pedagogical approaches and psychological potential when using new methods in education.

Effective organization of education is of great importance in the use of modern research, scientific research and pedagogical methods in education. This study provides recommendations for future teachers to improve their creativity skills.

Keywords: Competence, creativity, education, pedagogical methods, teacher skills, psychological potential, psychological research, pedagogical research.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ И КРЕАТИВНОСТИ В
ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

Аннотация. В данном исследовании представлена информация о фундаментальной природе компетентности и креативности в педагогическом образовании. В педагогической компетентности также отмечается, что от учителей требуется наличие креативности, педагогических подходов и психологического потенциала при использовании новых методов в образовании. Эффективная организация образования приобретает все большее значение при использовании современных исследований, научных разработок и педагогических методов в образовании. В исследовании даны рекомендации будущим учителям по совершенствованию их творческих навыков.

Ключевые слова: Компетентность, креативность, образование, педагогические методы, педагогическое мастерство, психологический потенциал, психологическое исследование, педагогическое исследование.

PEDAGOGIK KOMPETENTLIK VA KREATIVLIKNING TA'LIMDAGI
AHAMIYATI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqotda pedagogik ta'limda kompetentlik va kreativlikning asosiy mohiyati haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Shuningdek, ta'limda yangi metodlarni qo'llashda o'qituvchilardan kreativlik, pedagogiv yondashuvlar va psixologik salohiyat talab qilinishi pedagogik kompetentlikda keltirib o'tilgan. Ta'limda zamonaviy izlanishlar, ilmiy tadqiqotlar va

Aprel, 2025-Yil

pedagogik metodlardan foydalanishda ta'limning samarali tashkil qilinishi muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Ushbu taqdiqotda bo'lajak o'qituvchilarga kreativlik mahoratini oshirishda tavfsiyalar berilgan.

***Kalit so'zlar:** Kompetentlik, kreativlik, ta'lim, pedagogik metodlar, o'qituvchi mahorati, psixologik salohiyat, psixologik izlanishlar, pedagogik tadqiqotlar.*

Introduction

The concept of competence has entered the field of pedagogical education as a result of psychological research. Therefore, competence means how a specialist behaves in unconventional and unexpected situations, enters into dialogue, takes a new approach in interactions with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses conflicting information, and has a plan of action in consistently developing and complex processes. The main goal of pedagogical competence and creativity in education is to increase the intellectual potential of future teachers, enrich their worldview, introduce them to innovative educational technologies, new, innovative forms, methods and means of teaching, and create an opportunity to familiarize them with the qualities of pedagogical professional competence and the essence of creative abilities.

Developing the ability to adapt to the innovations of the modern world, to prepare the younger generation for the life of a constantly changing society and to actively participate in the processes of improving it in accordance with the requirements of the times is an important professional task of a teacher of a higher educational institution. Creativity encompasses the organization of the educational process, building a creative educational process, developing creative potential using educational technologies, and developing a balance of different methods, knowledge, and skills. The essence of creativity is that intelligence is a person's mental potential, while creativity is the ability to freely use this mental potential in a goal-oriented manner. The teacher is a person who is based on modern approaches to organizing educational processes on a scientific and methodological basis, ensuring the activity of students and coordinating their activities, ensuring the quality and effectiveness of educational processes, has high moral qualities, is able to analyze and objectively evaluate himself and his activities, has a rich philosophical and spiritual outlook, psychological, pedagogical and organizational and technological potential, as well as the skills to collect, analyze, objectively evaluate, process and exchange information, ensure the activity of learners in problematic situations arising in pedagogical processes and coordinate their activities, have the skills to foresee the effectiveness of the educational process based on the preliminary identification of factors that negatively affect

April, 2025-Yil

the effectiveness of pedagogical processes and student activity, and has the necessary skills in organizing and managing, coordinating, and ensuring the activity of subjects of the educational process on a scientific basis. It is desirable to have knowledge, skills, and qualifications. The tasks of the pedagogical direction of pedagogical competence and creativity are as follows:

- To make future teachers aware of the organizational, technical and didactic capabilities of modern innovative educational technologies, to organize pedagogical methods through the use of innovative teaching technologies in educational practice,
- To form pedagogical skills and psychological qualifications for the consistent development of pedagogical competence qualities and creative abilities; to create opportunities for future teachers to become aware of the ways to substantiate, create and effectively implement pedagogical innovations in practice;
- To ensure the activity of future teachers in the teaching process through pedagogical methods, to improve the quality of education, and to increase efficiency.

The Fundamentals of Pedagogical Competence and Creativity introduces the essence and important foundations of methodological technologies based on pedagogical education, the future teacher acquires the skills to effectively and purposefully apply pedagogical technologies in professional activities, and gains experience in rationally designing the educational process.

He also becomes aware of the ways to substantiate, create and effectively implement pedagogical innovations in practice. The subject of the Fundamentals of Pedagogical Competence and Creativity is considered as the content, form, pedagogical methods and means of forming the professional competence of future teachers. Professional competence in pedagogy is the process of acquiring knowledge, skills and competencies necessary for the implementation of professional activities by a specialist and their high-level application in practice. Professional competence implies not the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the mastery of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent area. Competence also requires the constant enrichment of professional knowledge, the ability to learn new information, the ability to understand important social demands, the ability to search for new information, process it, and apply it in one's work. The modernization of the educational strategy does not imply contrasting competence with knowledge, skills and abilities, but rather the ability to apply them in practice: "The concept of competence is a broad application of the concepts of knowledge, skills and competence, which includes in its composition (in fact, we are not talking about competence as a simple adaptive set of knowledge - the meaning of the concepts of competence - skills means several other concepts).

Aprél, 2025-Yil

The concept of competence includes not only the cognitive and operational-technological component, but also the motivational, moral, social and behavioral components. Therefore, an important condition for the development of creative abilities in learners through interactive teaching methods and technologies is the creation of a free-creative environment in the educational process, the establishment of a learning process based on the joint relations and mutual cooperation of professors, teachers and learners. There are a number of factors that develop creative abilities in students, some of which can be cited below:

- Developing teachers' creative thinking skills, forming creative activity, strengthening the search and problem-based research directions of the educational process;
- Organizing situations for students to creatively solve problems and develop creative activities;
- Achieving students' approach to the experience of creative activity as a professional necessity and a component of the content of future professional activity;
- Directing the process of developing students' professional skills and abilities to work on interactive methods and technologies, in which they can demonstrate independent creative activity, obtain independent knowledge, self-education, self-knowledge, gain their own position, activate students' abilities to work independently, and achieve their creative thinking in this process;
- creating a conducive creative and collaborative environment for students to demonstrate their creative abilities, etc.

There are the following criteria for determining the level of development of creative abilities in students: the determination of motivation for creative activity; the development of creative thinking skills; the formation of creative qualities; the organization of the process of practical creative activity; the formation of specialized creativity, etc. Creativity can be defined as: the desire for creativity, a creative approach to life, constant critical reflection and analysis of oneself. Based on modern psychological and pedagogical dictionaries, a teacher's creativity can be defined as the level of creative approach and knowledge in his thoughts, feelings, communication, and a particular type of activity. A teacher's creativity is his ability to find various original ideas in strict, limited or loosely limited conditions. Analysis of scientific literature allows us to distinguish the following interrelated structural components of creativity: Creativity is manifested in the creative aspiration, creative ability, creative goal, direction, and self-control of the teacher in his creative activity, and indicates that he is becoming a mature, developing, growing person with self-activity and self-control.

April, 2025-Yil

The creative competence of a teacher is reflected as his general characteristic. It is considered the initial condition and result of creative activity. This quality expresses the ability and readiness of a person to self-expression. The competence of a teacher is the manifestation of his theoretical and practical knowledge, skills and qualifications, worldview, beliefs and all personal individual socio-psychological qualities. One of the important factors ensuring the quality and effectiveness of education is the competence of a teacher in his subject.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that pedagogical competence and creativity are manifested on the basis of the pedagogical adaptation system. These are: scientific knowledge, psychological potential, pedagogical knowledge, creative approach to finding effective solutions to any problem situations, manifestation of high social psychological characteristics in the process of educational and educational impact, continuous self-development through the effective use of one's intellectual, cognitive, emotional, moral potential, learning and internal psychological reserve; positive emotional attitude towards society and people, nature, and being, which consists of the experience of transition to positive thinking.

REFERENCES

1. Turemuratova, Aziza, Rita Kurbanova, and Barno Saidboyeva. "EDUCATIONAL TRADITIONS IN SHAPING THE WORLDVIEW OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN FOLK PEDAGOGY." *Modern Science and Research* 2.10 (2023): 318-322.
2. Kurbanova, R. J., and B. E. Saidboeva. "MAKTAB VA OILADA ESTETIK TARBIYANI SHAKLLANTIRISH JARAYONIDA O'QUVCHILARNING AKSILOGIK DUNYOQARASHINI RIVOJLANTIRISH." *Inter education & global study* 9 (2024): 114-121.
3. Jarilkapovich, Matjanov Aman. "USE OF PEDAGOGICAL METHODS BASED ON THE MODERN EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM TO INCREASE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF EDUCATION." *European International Journal of Pedagogics* 4.06 (2024): 26-33.
4. Jarilkapovich, Matjanov Aman. "Program Technology for Choosing an Effective Educational Methodology Based on Modern Pedagogical Research in The Educational System." *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS* 6.02 (2025): 30-33.
5. Turemuratova, Aziza, Ziyra Kalilaeva, and Gulayim Xojanova. "IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL SKILLS OF A PSYCHOLOGIST-TRAINER AND DEVELOPING A

Aprel, 2025-Yil

- METHODOLOGY FOR PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING." Modern Science and Research 4.4 (2025): 782-787.
6. Turemuratova, Aziza, Amina Turganbayeva, and Kundiz Allambergenova. "PSIXOLOG TRENERNING KASBIY KO'NIKMALARI VA PSIXOLOGIK SALOHIYATINI OSHIRUVCHI AMALIY TRENINGLAR." Modern Science and Research 4.4 (2025): 884-890.
 7. Turemuratova, Aziza, Lazzat Jubatqanova, and Nasiba Joldasbaeva. "PSIXOTERAPIVTIK TOVARLAR BILAN ISHLASHNING ASOSIY QOIDALARI HAQIDA UMUMIY MA'LUMOTLAR." Modern Science and Research 4.4 (2025): 251-254.
 8. Turemuratova, Aziza, Ayman Kaipbergenova, and Gulmira Niyazova. "PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT METHODS THROUGH PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING AND THE USE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING METHODS." Modern Science and Research 4.4 (2025): 142-146.
 9. Kurbanova, Rita. "PEDAGOGICAL CRITERIA FOR THE FORMATION OF AN AXIOLOGICAL WORLDVIEW IN SCHOOLCHILDREN." Modern Science and Research 4.4 (2025): 714-721.
 10. Turemuratova, Aziza, Renat Urazimbetov, and Miyassar Babajanova. "IMPROVING STUDENTS' COLLABORATIVE SKILLS THROUGH PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING AND BASIC RULES FOR THE PRACTICE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING." Modern Science and Research 4.4 (2025): 532-538.
 11. Turemuratova, Aziza, Qoniratbay Bazarbaev, and Laylo Kurbanova. "THE CONCEPT OF PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING GROUPS AND THE PRACTICE OF GROUP TRAINING FOR A COLLABORATIVE STUDENT TEAM." Modern Science and Research 4.4 (2025): 152-158.
 12. Turumbetova, Zamira, and Dinara Abdiraxmanova. "INFLUENCE OF THE SOCIAL ENVIRONMENT ON THE BEHAVIOR OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN." Modern Science and Research 3.5 (2024): 1196-1199.